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Accreditation and Validation of Professional Qualifications: Monitoring of the Process by Insertion Companies

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Abstract

People at risk for exclusion and vulnerable populations have serious difficulties in accessing the ordinary labour market. Their work insertion is more complicated than that of people with high employability capacities. People's social exclusion risk could be reduced if, among other measures, their access would be facilitated to the accreditation and validation of their professional competences. This work shows how Work Integration Social Enterprises support people at risk for exclusion in obtaining the accreditation and validation of their professional qualifications. We critically describe and analyse the process, concluding that the initiative breaks with the perception of accreditation and validation of competences as an individual action. Instead, this process introduces the idea of a multi-party process for integration that returns the individual to its societal dimension.

Keywords

accreditation; validation; qualifications; guidance; work integration social enterprises

1 Transitions to the validation and accreditation of professional qualifications

European training policies ascribe great importance to the recognition of learning that has not been acquired in school but in non-formal or informal environments. Recommendations made by the European Council (2012) are aimed at promoting the validation of this learning with attention to social cohesion, among other considerations.

However, lifelong learning does not always reflect patterns of social justice. There is evidence that younger people, those who have high education levels, those who have jobs, or those who work in highly skilled occupations are the ones that are more often involved in lifelong learning programmes (Boyadjieva and Ilieva-Trichkova, 2017; Roosmaa and Saar, 2012). In this regard, Bukodi (2016) argues that lifelong learning mainly serves as a way of maintaining rather than reducing inequalities associated with social origins. In fact, as Walker (2012) notes, the more privileged classes accumulate more resources and advantages, even in terms of education. Some authors reckon that this strong critique made of lifelong learning programmes also affects the system of validation and accreditation of professional qualifications. Marhuenda and Bernard (2008) consider that the certification, validation and accreditation of learning outcomes in the labour market will be less accessible to people with lower social status, those who are more vulnerable, less educated and with less formal accreditation.

The common pathway for obtaining the certification, validation and accreditation of professional qualifications is not concerned about the learning process carried out by individuals to get those qualifications. This process typically focuses exclusively on results; that is, the process only evaluates learning outcomes that can be observed (Souto-Otero, 2012; Tejada, 2007). These procedures are directed at those who request accreditation, placing the responsibility at the individual level (Duvekot, 2014). However, an alternative approach is possible wherein the process of certification, validation and accreditation of professional qualifications does not only fall solely on the individual. We posit that the responsibility of the process can be shared among different agents: the individual him/herself, public administrations and companies such as Work Integration Social Enterprises (WISEs).

In the Spanish context, the Organic Law 5/2002 of the 19th of June on Qualifications and Vocational Training (2002) introduced the opportunity to evaluate and accredit professional qualifications in Spain (article 2). This process did not materialize until seven years later with the approval of Royal Decree 1224/2009 of the 17th of July, which established the procedure and requirements for the evaluation and accreditation of professional competences acquired through work experience or non-formal training contexts. This regulation opened the possibility for certifying available and verifiable professional competences included in the National Catalogue of Professional Qualifications (CNQ).

This process seems to be a resource of special interest given the high percentage of the active population that does not have certificates of professional qualifications. Figures from the Economically Active Population Survey, Quarter 2/2018, show that 63.32% of the population over 16 years of age does not have this training. These groups are widely represented in WISEs, which are entities that hire groups at risk for social exclusion. This hiring is for a period never exceeding three years in order to facilitate transitions to the ordinary labour market, where individuals are exempt from social protection.

We find few examples in which the responsibility of the validation and accreditation of qualifications process is shared between the individual and other agents. We could cite the case of Mercadona, a commercial chain in the food sector, or the Federico Ozanam Foundation, an entity in the third sector, but these are isolated cases. This work analyses how WISEs support integration workers (IWs) in this process. Our objective is to understand how organizations that operate in the Third Sector, under the scheme of Social Economy, assume a joint responsibility to help their workers, who are in vulnerable situations, to obtain the accreditation of their qualifications.

This paper presents advances on the state of the R&D project “Processes of training, monitoring, qualification and personal development in Work Integration Social Enterprises: innovation in social inclusion from employment” (EDU2013-45919-R, EMPLEA). One may find among its objectives “To identify and analyze the evaluation of Production Worker (PW) and Accompanying Worker (AW) to Integration Workers (IWs), in those moments of inflection of the learning process at the WISE”. To fulfil this purpose, one of the research aims is to understand the involvement of WISEs in accreditation processes.

Previous research has developed the improved proposal of mapping occupations to be accredited with WISEs and identified the limitations of the process that greatly affect the most vulnerable groups. These limitations include limited incorporation of level 1 qualifications in the CNQ, scarce calls for places at this level of qualification and the absence of criteria for positive discrimination that would allow the participation of these groups (Chisvert-Tarazona, Ros-Garrido, Córdoba-Iñesta and Marhuenda, 2015). This uncertain panorama places the most vulnerable groups at greater risk for social exclusion. The performance of these groups during the teaching-learning processes within WISEs could be vital to benefit their access to the system of validation and accreditation of professional qualifications.

2 Research question and methodology

The following is our research question: Are WISEs prepared to share joint responsibility with IWs to facilitate the certification, validation and accreditation of their professional qualifications? A positive answer will allow us to consider the importance of consolidating resources to support the validation and accreditation of qualification processes by enterprises under the safety net of the social economy.

To answer the research question, we base our empirical study on Eraut's theory of learning trajectories (Eraut, 2009; Eraut & Hirsh, 2007). This theory considers workplace learning and its link with performance to understand how organizations can better facilitate workplace learning and proposes a conceptual tool to observe professional competences. Therefore, our methodology was qualitative and longitudinal. Specifically, the longitudinal study was carried out between 2015-2017. We visited ten WISEs. They were visited three times throughout the research period. Within these WISEs, a total of forty-seven IWs were observed in-depth in real work situations. Additionally, we conducted 32 semi-structured interviews, 11 with PWs and 21 with AWs. The results provide information about the strategies and practices implemented by WISEs to facilitate the process of validation and accreditation of their workers' qualifications.

3 Results

Our study shows how the WISEs work to inform, train and make IWs aware of the importance of the accreditation and validation of professional competences. Indeed, WISEs have participated in training workshops to understand the procedures to formally assess and accredit vocational qualification. Therefore, we can confirm that WISEs assume joint responsibility of this process. However, in practice, limited progress has been made in guiding and counselling IWs to facilitate, in an understandable way, all the information about accreditation and methodology for obtaining recognition of their professional competences. WISEs are shown to have good intentions, but they have not put these intentions into good practise.

Based on the information gathered during the research phase, 9 out of 10 WISEs have been able to identify professional qualifications that could be accredited according to the CNQ. Most of these are occupations that require low-level qualifications; only two companies have been able to identify level 2¹ qualifications.

In three WISEs, AWs have demonstrated a clear intention to obtain the accreditation of their competences. These are institutions that, as a first step, have offered training to IWs with certificates of professionalism, inside or outside of their facilities. In 6 WISEs, the need by companies to improve training to certify, at least, some unit of competence is explicitly recognized. The main obstacles to progress in the integration of accreditation processes are i) the need to maintain a high rate of work (they are enterprises that must be productive and not only well thought of socially); ii) the geographic location of the company and; iii) the lack of opportunities and support. WISEs, to help candidates understand their needs for certification and to identify their professional competence, need knowledge, tools and time to help individuals to provide evidence of their labour and formative history.

¹ At the European level, there are more levels of qualification than in Spain. The eight levels of the framework cover all types of qualifications in Spain. Level descriptors are defined in terms of knowledge, skills and competences. The four upper levels are compatible with the levels of the Spanish Qualifications Framework for Higher Education, based on the Dublin descriptors (Law 5/2002 and Royal Law 1128/2003, and their modifications at Royal Law 1416/2005, that stands the National Qualifications Framework).

It is surprising that in five out of ten companies, IWs do not know the processes for accreditation of competences. It is especially striking that the initiatives to obtain Graduate certifications for compulsory secondary education have not been successfully developed.

Since the beginning of 2017, we have actively participated in the design of a guide to facilitate the processes of accreditation of professional competences to be fully adapted to the needs of the IC. This guide has been promoted by the State Federations of Insertion Companies: the Federation of Business Associations of Insertion Companies (FAEDEI) and the Spanish Association of Social Economy and Solidarity Rescuers (AERESS). The guide has been developed by a mixed working group that engages members of insertion companies of both federations and members of the 'Transitions Research Group' at Universitat de València. This guide has a simple didactic format that includes examples that facilitate an understanding of the procedure. In order to disseminate the results of that guide, the processes of accreditation have been included as a main theme in two state meetings aimed at accompanying personnel in these third sector institutions.

Based on these results, we can say that WISEs are aware of the importance of these processes and are interested in assuming joint responsibility.

4 Conclusions

These results show that efforts are headed in the right direction. Although there is still a long way to go, the WISE map of occupations that can more easily be accredited in the Spanish context has helped to start the process of validating and accrediting certain qualifications (Chisvert-Tarazona, Ros-Garrido, Córdoba-Iñesta and Marhuenda Fluixá, 2015).

The results highlight an institutional proactivity among WISEs. Business federations are leading the appropriation of validation and accreditation procedures in four important ways: (1) participation in research projects that include accreditation as a main goal; (2) development of guides and handbooks adapted to the WISE context (Guillera-Marco and Chisvert-Tarazona, 2018); (3) political actions to promote positive discrimination for bringing more opportunities for vulnerable people to access validation and accreditation procedures; and (4) training WISE managers and AWs in the validation and accreditation procedures.

In practice, we find WISEs to be widely concerned with guaranteeing the certification of apprenticeships. However, WISEs have experienced serious challenges with leveraging the benefits of the procedure. The analysed WISEs have not taken advantage of those WISEs in the surrounding area that have demonstrated the possibility for integrating accreditation processes in teaching contexts.

By definition, the accreditation process obviates the place from which learning has been accessed. However, we have found indications that these institutions have the explicit objective of introducing accompaniment in the processes for accreditation of competencies. The competency learning process accessed by IWs in their companies may benefit from this collective effort.

This initiative breaks with the perception of accreditation and validation of competences as an individual action while it introduces the idea of community, providing a way for integration that returns the individual to its societal dimension. Therefore, individuals and enterprises have a joint responsibility.

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